

Seaming hands: The meaning and value of the handmade in contemporary fashion

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ABSTRACT

The perpetual crisis of subjectivity experienced today means that the modern self is always partial and relative to what is “other.” This corresponds to the more individualized and coded values relevant to what is currently regarded as “original” or “authentic,” notions that are inseparable from luxury in fashion. This article analyzes the handmade in contemporary fashion as the product of liminality and our reflexive response to it – a necessary process in the renewal of existing values. This analysis derives from my experience of making a series of seamless woven garments, entirely by hand. The handcrafted elements and seamlessness of these garments, qualities traditionally associated with luxury production, are reappraised in this article, as the process which offers a luxury experience for the maker: the act of making becomes a method of displacement, creating a space for contemplation and self-reflection, which is then communicated to the users via the material trace left by the making hands. Certain modes of making and using material objects can thus be seen as our own “rites of passage,” which heighten the awareness of the link between self and other in contemporary society. This article therefore suggests an alternative notion of luxury, one which reflects the value arising from attentive modes of interaction with material objects and people, and the reflexivity this experience

allows. This new luxury is thus a more graspable one, as it can be self-generated here and now.

KEYWORDS: seamless, liminal, luxury, reflexivity, handmade

Introduction

Fashion, viewed as a product of a post-industrial culture and the urbanization of nineteenth-century Europe, exists in the dialectic relationship between high-end fashion (ready-to-wear and made-to-measure) and its diffused, mass-produced copies, which generate vogue and accelerate change. As the copies displace the original, high fashion continually creates differences which distinguish and demarcate itself from its copies, which are the now widely accepted norm.

Fashion is therefore the cultural field which effectively demonstrates “the interplay between originality and the acceptance of tradition as the basis for inventiveness, the interplay between separateness and union” (Winnicott 2005: 134). This interplay is the process of transition – a fundamental human condition accelerated and accentuated in modernity – potentially leading to a renewal, to the rearrangement of old elements into different patterns.

This article will investigate the modern condition, characterized by its constant rapid-paced change, and contemporary society’s diverse response to this: the fetishistic worship of luxury goods; the automated mode of production; the globalized luxury production and consumption; the increasing interest in the handmade, custom-made and slow production. It then reflects on the position occupied by the handmade within the contemporary fashion system, in which contrasting production/consumption patterns coexist, examining whether the handmade may be “a transitional phenomenon” brought about by reflexivity. In order to emphasize the central importance of materiality in this phase of transition, references from anthropology (the material/corporeal representations used in rites of passage), psychoanalysis (Winnicott’s Transitional Objects) and art theory (Surrealist’s “the mechanical-commodified”) are adapted. The conclusions drawn reveal our changing attitude towards originality or authenticity, notions inseparable from what is considered luxury in fashion today.

This analysis derives from my own experience of making garments entirely by hand. In my practice, putting together the cut pieces of industrially woven fabric by hand results in a scar-like threshold which is neither seamed nor seamless, and yet is both. This act of making new links and securing edges via the repeated touch of the needle on the skin and through the cloth implies making as “marking.” The woven seam is thus the materialization of reflective practice, which concretizes the meeting of self and other, past and present, the original and its reproduction, keeping them separate yet connected. It is a material token, which leads us to reflect on the value and meaning of the things we make and use today, and how they “make” us (Figure 1).

Neither this nor that, and yet is both

Arnold van Gennep’s notion of liminality sees life itself as an expansive transitional stage where people separate and reunite, die and are reborn, in changing forms and conditions (van Gennep 1960: 189), and “beneath a multiplicity of forms, the typical pattern of the rites of passage always recurs” (van Gennep 1960: 191). Through the threefold structure of these rites of passage – separation, transition and incorporation (van Gennep 1960: 11) – the crucial changes in life are clearly acknowledged. This “marking” of transition with rites is considered to aid the individual along the process which “may be upsetting to the life of the group and the individual” (Kimball 1960: ix).

Victor Turner shares van Gennep’s view of life as a transitional passage, during which undoing and dissolution are accompanied by processes of growth, transformation and the reformulation of old elements into new patterns:

It is interesting to note how ... logically antithetical processes of death and growth may be represented by the same tokens, for example, by huts and tunnels that are at once tombs and wombs, ... by nakedness (which is at once the mark of a newborn infant and a corpse prepared for burial) ... This coincidence of opposite processes and notions in a single representation characterizes the peculiar unity of the liminal: that which is neither this nor that, and yet is both. (Turner 1970: 99)

“The peculiar unity” of the liminal stage would then mean the meeting and processing of differences and contradictions before starting anew. This process is acted out in the way that neophytes are *cut off* from the rest of the group during a rite of passage, often accompanied by *cuts* and *wounds* on the body, and kept on *the edge* of the territorial boundary for a period of reflection before being reincorporated into the group.

The images accompanying this article illustrate a particular way in which cut pieces of fabric are put together “seamlessly” to be constructed into garments. This seaming method – cutting through a piece of woven cloth, purposefully fraying the cut edge and then reweaving the individual frayed threads into another cut edge of cloth – is a reminder of many tokens of cutting, passing through and connecting observed in rites of passage. The possible affinity between the human skin and the surface of a garment formed through repeated use renders this comparison particularly compelling.

Moreover, for the maker, the process of seaming is also a transitional experience – a state of temporary separation from the world, investing time, effort and attention that goes far beyond the bare necessities of making. As the material held by the hands is slowly transformed through the repeated touches of the needle on and through the surface of the cloth, and on the surface of the body – not unlike scarification or tattooing – the maker also goes through a change.

It appears that certain concrete material representations possess the powerful capacity to act on the emotions and imaginations of individuals. This affective content of objects, especially those which recall human bodily aspects – form, skin, texture, movement etc. – can be strangely compelling. The cut, change and renewal represented in the “seamless” garments illustrated here are suggested as a reminder of the aforementioned fundamental human condition and, in turn, as a possible indicator of the new notion of luxury – the objects and experiences that we truly value and aspire to today (Figure 2).

A permanent passage

With perpetual change regarded as the characteristic modern condition, we are in permanent liminality, processing change with various methods of cuts and markings of our own. To make oneself at home in constant disintegration and renewal, the modern subject needs to somehow self-reflect during each change in order to rethink existing values. Anthony Giddens points out “the reflexive appropriation of knowledge” as the main cause of the uncertain and disorientated condition of modernity (Giddens 1990: 53).¹ More frequent reflexive states caused by perpetual change seem to further accelerate this rate of change and its disorientating effects.

Therefore the modern self is always incomprehensive and partial, and is a relative notion dependent on what is other. This insubstantial self, a perpetual stranger to oneself, thus desperately longs for something stable to cling to, yearning to form more grounded links with others, yet the ambiguous boundary between self and other means that this other, as much as the self, constantly oscillates between nearness and distance. The brief sense of relief coming from self-understanding is quickly unsettled when one can no longer find the self that used to be. Unable to find a home in the self, we set off on a new search. “‘Home’ is not a physical place but a mobile need; wherever one is, home is always to be found somewhere else” (Sennett 2011: 88).

The handcraft labor used in textile and garment production is traditionally associated with luxury production. Even today the term ‘couture’, to sew, denotes made-to-measure garments and *haute couture*, a term preserved for the highest form of fashionable design and dressmaking, is considered the ultimate luxury. The extensive use of handcraft is typically the element that “justifies” its unattainable price for the most. This act of making by hand, however, is suggested in this article as a process which offers a luxury experience for the maker: while temporarily retreating into the self, or a “home,” we can gain a particular vantage point of the past and the present, and a sharp awareness of the fast-moving fashion system.

The handmade: a resting place

Increasing interest in the bespoke and the handmade in fashion seems to be the result of anonymous, transient, virtual interactions that have replaced much of today's actual face-to-face interactions. Rather than being the expression of an anti-modern attitude or a nostalgia, this growing interest seems to reveal the urgent need and desire to *contemplate*² – perhaps the same impetus that changes a neophyte during the transitional period – as the repeated renewal of self-knowledge is “the perpetual human task,” as Winnicott (2005: 3) suggests.

Winnicott's notion of “Transitional Objects and Transitional Phenomena” theorizes the process through which an infant self emerges from the fusion with, and separation from, the other. The “third area” of transition is neither inner world nor outer reality. The infant in this third area is not required to neatly demarcate the two while oscillating in between: eventually it creates the boundary of subject and object, self and other. Suggesting that this repeated “reality testing,” i.e. the oscillation between inner world and outer reality, is a developmental necessity, Winnicott describes this as a process of generating “edges” through the experience of overlapping edges. The notion of “Transitional Objects and Transitional Phenomena” implies the potentiality implicit in the temporary dissolution of the boundary between self and other, as well as the central role that material culture plays in this unending renewal of subjectivities throughout a person's life. This transitional stage is experienced throughout life, in the “play” of childhood for example, and in what he calls the “cultural experience”³ of adulthood.

In this article, I am especially interested in how the process of making can be understood as an aspect of the cultural domain in which this reality-testing takes place. Following Winnicott's theory that this intermediate phase is triggered as well as aided by the concrete materiality of Transitional Objects which act as the baby's “resting place,” in which he or she gains the capacity to seek and bear solitude, I suggest that making by hand can create a resting place where one can contemplate whilst being in contact with material.

The illustrated handwoven seams are the materialization of reflective practice – the meeting of the maker's two hands and the material, the touch of the needle on the surface of the cloth and the surface of the body, concretizes

the meeting of self and other in a material dimension of time and place. As intuitive and insightful responses are triggered by the process of fraying and reweaving fabric, the woven stitches turn into an ethnography of the maker's self, blurring the line between making and writing, between making and thinking. Even in a public space, the maker can temporarily be cocooned within a self-generated solitude, solely created by the attentive mode of being (Figure 3).

For those who voluntarily choose handmade methods for tasks that can now be achieved by machines, the process often puts them in a reflective mode: the maker gets into the "edge" of the boundary of the fashion system that constantly and frantically overproduces, for a market that over-consumes. This distinguishes the contemporary handmade, or bespoke, from that of earlier times. Displacement gives us a sharp awareness of the state we are in, revealing the joints in the seemingly solid and smooth system, letting us see how this illusion is constructed. In the transformative, cocoon-like "third area," which provides us with a sharper awareness of the present, the ostentatious luxury heightened by abstract images, as well as the ungraspable "authentic real" we crave, are both revealed as illusions – a state from which renewed values may emerge.

Moreover, within the speed and exposure of modern life, the privilege of being left alone, of being "offline," for a period of time, is easily agreed upon. When time is the most precious "commodity" today (Bailey 2011: 36), slowness, spending as much attention and effort as one desires on a single task, is an ultimate luxury – graspable, solely with an individual mode of being, here and now.

The seam(less) and luxury

Although fashion is one of the most rapidly moving industries, it still depends heavily on a significant amount of manual labor in its manufacturing process. Many parts of the process are now mechanized, but the most essential operation – the putting together of a garment – is yet to be automated. The attempt to devise a seamless woven garment was motivated by the need to reduce production costs by eliminating human labor, which still remains its main aim.

Seams in the garment therefore inevitably involve the human hand, and are where the last traces of human operation – mistakes, variations, improvisation – may manifest. At a less material level, the placement of seams complementing the chosen material, as well as the wearer’s body, directly connects to the designer’s ability to transform raw material into a garment relevant to actuality.

In Western culture, seamlessness is a quality traditionally associated with luxury goods. In standard clothing, functional seams are ideally unnoticeable: a successful seam creates an illusion of an undivided surface, and garments are lined to protect the vulnerable edges and to hide the unsightly evidence of assembly. Well-seamed things, therefore, typically represent well-made things. The masterful execution of seams and joints has always been evidence of great craftsmanship, evoking the immaculate creation of *deus faber* (God the creator) as opposed to the labored assembly of man the creator (*homo faber*).⁴ Unlike divine creation, however, humans can only repair discontinuous fragments by meticulously joining them. When the process of putting together is kept intact in the resulting artefact, the visible and invisible traces reveal the way the maker repaired and negotiated the emerging contingencies. In this sense, a finished work is the intact trace of the process in itself – the chaotic, non-linear movements, with irrational and speculative leaps, which are part of the making of both artefacts and the self. The newly made object thus borrows its shape from the maker’s touches that have put it together.

Not only the trace of the maker but also the trace of the wearer can manifest in seams. Kitty Hauser explains how FBI research on the identification of denim trousers from surveillance footage effectively reveals the criminal: although the criminal’s face is invisible to the camera, the individuating properties of the creases and wear patterns of his jeans are clearly visible, most prominently at the seams and hems. “These are likened by the investigator to barcodes, which may be unique to each garment” (Hauser 2005: 154–5). The trace of making and using left in the seams renders even the most industrialized production unique.

The Belgian designer Martin Margiela has developed sweaters with the shape of elbows, breasts and other traces of the body “as if someone’s grandmother had worn it hundreds of times, as if someone had found it years

later in some attic.” After years of research, he used heat-mouldable yarns and cooked the sweaters on an oversized dummy, in the industrial oven of an automotive factory (Wilson 2008). In this project, in which Margiela replicated the traces of use, he seems to have wanted to connect the trace of making with the trace of wearing. The research and work involved in the process, the trace of the maker, meets the invaluable personal meanings and memories of the wearer, suggesting the possible affinity between the two. For makers, the affinity they have built up with the material during the process of making renders the products inalienable despite their status as commodity. The enduring link means that the maker pays the utmost attention to the product so that it lasts, accumulating the traces of its users. Both the maker and the user thus contribute to the making of authentic garments: the authentic qualities originating from the material evidence of making and using, and the emotional and sensuous responses triggered by these processes. This is the compelling aspect that I would associate with the new notion of luxury: we are inclined to identify with anything whose external configuration suggests our own body. Certain objects and images therefore have the privilege of disturbing the affectivity of people and of arousing in them a shared irrational curiosity (Caillois 2003: 70, 80, 81).

Designers in the “deconstruction movement” during the 1980s and 1990s subverted both kinds of trace: like the aforementioned sweaters, the traces of consumption which are usually absent in new products were purposefully added, to achieve a “used” look. Rei Kawakubo used boiled wool, which Ann Demeulemeester later adopted in her poetic rendering of the punk aesthetic. Margiela’s frequent use of second-hand material (a leather butcher’s apron reworked into an evening gown etc.), shredded jeans or garment surfaces with mould accentuate the value and meaning which are added through use. The trace of production was celebrated by using linings as outer layers, leaving hems raw and exposing seams so that they are rough on the outside. Less manifestly, the repeated handling during the long process of making by hand “ages” the material. This emergent, rather than purposeful, trace of the maker can be regarded as a condensation of the process (Figure 4).

The commodified trace

This appeal of the trace, the mutual shaping between wearer and garment and between maker and garment, is widely exploited in contemporary fashion: the poetic origin of the “used look” is forgotten when adopted in the mass-consumption market, which focuses on visual appearance alone. This look, now taken for granted, is an emblem of the changing relationship between user and object, mirroring the pattern of change in the maker’s relationship with the object, as the market moves toward more mass-produced one.

Even “some luxury brands strive to associate craftsmanship with their product ranges, yet they are mass producing in such a way that the artisan skills are no longer evident” (Montgomery 2012: 6). Skilled craftspeople are placed on an industrial production line, taking part in isolated roles, without being involved in the whole process. Often the products are made in far-flung places, at the lowest cost, to be disguised with “made-in ...” labels which are no longer considered to be a genuine reflection of the garments’ provenance.

This tendency unfortunately further exploits workers from developing countries, who do not benefit from the disproportionate added value. This situation inevitably points up the uncomfortable link between globalized production and distribution, and the notion of luxury. Although mass-produced objects can potentially be imbued with individual value and authenticity, it is difficult to ignore the unethical and unsustainable aspects of the production process.

In this context, the seam represents the ambiguity of value introduced by the process of making. The act of seaming turns raw material with a relatively straightforward market value into a garment with added value that is socially and culturally determined. Excessive value added by the distorted notion of authenticity, and by the artificially fabricated trace, is mirrored in the exploitation of the maker–user relationship that often occurs with made-to-measure garments. Bespoke goods appeal to the user’s desire to be included in a process of making, where a desired fit is achieved through face-to-face interaction. This encourages the consumer’s interest in the maker, where it came from and how it was made. This then connects to the experiential values of buying, using and owning carefully made objects.

Yet this is not strictly the case with some of the bespoke and the personalized garments now available to the masses: “Burberry Bespoke” offers an opportunity for online customization of its trench coat, now available in 12 million iterations (The Future Laboratory 2012: 11). Lower-priced brands, such as Levi’s, Converse, Nike and many others, also offer online customization. But all these examples are devoid of first-hand interaction, where the solutions for users’ needs would be improvised, and makers would feel rewarded by their satisfaction. The fabricated trace in these examples is created as an abstract image, rather than through a process of genuine engagement.

Contemporary society’s fetishistic worship of ostentatious luxury goods, aroused by the inflated advertising campaigns ascribing almost mythic quality to the luxury brands, fires up conspicuous consumption as if one’s social and cultural status depended on it. The illusion that one’s identity is determined by buying and owning objects, the value of which is predetermined by others, is only effective when the concrete materiality of things and human corporeality remain forgotten. Peter Stallybrass criticizes this commodity fetishism as worship of the transcendental value that erases both the making and the wearing of a garment:

... a society that consumes ever more concrete human bodies. The abstraction of this society is represented by the commodity form itself. For commodity becomes a commodity not as a thing but as an exchange value. It achieves its purest form, in fact, when most emptied out of particularity and thingliness. (Stallybrass 1998: 183)

Fashion as a system is a symbol of capitalism, where garments can exist only as abstract value and image, but the possibility of particular, affective and subjective luxury is always offered at the tangible material level of the garment: this depends on the mode of producing, selling, buying, wearing, keeping and handling the garments, as tangible material that gets shaped by us and that shapes us in turn. The nature of our relationship with material things determines the abstractness or concreteness of these things, as much as that of our own. Without the physical and emotional trace of making bodies and using bodies,

the products remain as mere garments, devoid of personal value and authenticity.

Walter Benjamin considers commodity fetishism as “empathy with exchange value” (Benjamin 1980: 140). There seems to be a fine line between commodity fetishism and the anthropological notion of the fetish as suggested by Pietz (1985, 1987, 1988). Both involve empathy with inorganic matter and a form of “consumption,” but the difference lies in the abstract or concrete nature of the thing valued. Benjamin seems to have been aware of the workings of the West African fetish, which was sometimes believed to take effect (going further than just wearing it) by being ingested, becoming a part of the body: it reveals the close link between respectful consumption of things and the respect for ourselves. The non-universal, subjective value of material things, encouraged by the affective content, can have a secret and irrational effect upon each individual. Empathy with the fetish would then mean empathizing with its ritual value by owning and using it while *identifying* with it. The fetish on the West African coast was difficult to put a price on, exasperating the European merchants, and was thus blamed for blocking the smooth flow of exchange. Yet given the relationship the owners have with their fetishes, how can one put a price on oneself?

Losing the edge

The importance of tactile interaction for babies and infants as analyzed in psychoanalytic studies⁵ implies that a lack of skin contact has a negative effect on the formation of subjectivity and social relationships. For adults, who incorporate much more of the space around them as bodily perimeter, reduced face-to-face interaction would certainly have various effects on their psychological make-up. In the absence of a concrete other, we are more desperate for the affirmation of our “edges” than ever. We need boundaries, while at the same time we do not always want to feel limited by these. Our relationship with the things with which we can identify through use console the yearning for the unique self, the marking of the “edge” established through repeated interaction.

With the rampant increase in carelessly distributed, disposable garments of increasingly poor quality, there is no time to accumulate the trace or to build up an affinity with garments. As the garments become merely items to throw away, we are slowly losing our skin along with the subjectivity inscribed in/on it. It is not the rapid fashion cycle which is to blame, but rather a mode of production and consumption which has no desire to keep and to reuse clothes (Figure 5).

Winnicott points out that the temporary weakening of the self's sense of boundaries can be enjoyed and tolerated as a "developmental necessity." However, at an excessive degree, it could entail a serious loss of subjectivity as witnessed in some types of schizophrenia. I would also compare this more serious loss of the edge with commodity fetishism as a pattern of consumption and the automatized mode of production that commodity fetishism tends to induce.

The Surrealist imagery of "the mechanical-commodified" evokes the reconfiguring of the human body as machine⁶ (Foster 1993: 126). In an ironic inversion of the mockery and demonization of the African fetish as depicted by Pietz (1985, 1987, 1988), the Surrealist notion of the "mechanical-commodified" mocked machine production and commodity fetishism. It was intended to recall the forgotten value of materiality in favor of abstract commodity exchange value in capitalist society, which became our demonic double, endlessly consuming our machine-like labor. In stark contrast to the anthropological notion of the fetish, the human dimension remains forgotten in commodity fetishism.

Hal Foster explains the attempt to erase human error, in order to achieve increased efficiency of production. This attempt evolves from disciplining the body in institutional settings, towards the uncanny processes of mechanization, generating a worker-as-machine in a modern industrial plant:

... automatic behavior [of the docile, manipulable body] was perfected in the factory and emblemized by the automaton. ... In 1738 [Jacques Vaucanson] presented his famous automatons ... in 1741 Vaucanson ... worked to mechanize fabric production (his

mechanical loom was the basis of the automatic Jacquard loom of 1801), and in 1756 he designed a silk factory near Lyons that, ... is often considered the first modern industrial plant. ... the central site where man-as-machine, worker-as-automaton, is produced. (Foster 1993: 131)

More consequential than the automation of production process itself, it seems, is the automated mode of makers. Just as the industrially produced garments possess the possibility of uniqueness, making by hand may also be reduced to mere automatism. When I make, I fear *and* anticipate unpredictability. Contingencies protect me from mindless repetition, and the work from being a mundane one. The handmade contains the poetic rhythm, which is irreproducible. It is as if the hands are thinking, forgetting, stopping and remembering. Human repetition deviates, bringing about differences rather than the identical. My inconsistency, the inability to reproduce the identical, renders my work uniquely my own. The purpose of repetition in making by hand is to break the rhythm while working within it. The maker submerges him/herself in the work and repeats the similar processes until his/her perceptibility reaches its fullest state, experiencing “the intangible differences within the persistent, transferable sameness of the reproduction” (Shiff 1997). Unlike mechanical reproduction, the maker’s own act of reproduction fine-tunes his/her perceptibility.

The unique quality of the handmade is thus a combined result of the laborious processes and irreproducible contingency, neither of which can be replicated in the modified versions of the mass-production market. This distinction lies in the quantity as well as the quality of labor, and, most importantly, in the attention and attitude of the makers involved in the process. This aspect is inseparable from the meaning of luxury today: whether hand- or machine-made, in a non-automatized mode of production each making hand is unique, as is each person-to-person relationship. The non-automatized touch and its trace personalize the garment surface, which cannot be objectively valued.

The “woven-in” seaming method depicted here essentially copies the Jacquard weave, which itself was the first mechanical reproduction of the woven tapestry – one of the most labor-intensive methods of textile production. The experience of copying mechanically produced fabric by using excessive labor, working between the pre- and postmodern modes of production, unwittingly led me to reflect on the place that the handmade occupies within the contemporary fashion system, as well as modes of production and consumption, and the link between the two. While existing seamless garment construction techniques invariably focus on cost-effectiveness, the handwoven tapestry method and the “weaving-in” techniques are utterly uneconomical. These contrasting modes of producing (or eliminating) seams reflect the ambiguity of the value of human labor in modernity. In the woven seams illustrated here, it is difficult to discern where the functional seaming stitches end and the decorative embroidery begins. The boundary between the “need” and the “want” is ambiguous. When the maker chooses to put “excess” attention and effort into making, beyond the basic “need” into making, how does it affect the value ascribed to the object? It might be useful to consider the values of two objects which are identical in their visual appearance and quality, yet made in different ways – one by hand and the other by 3D printing method, for instance. The value of man-made objects does not arise solely from the finished state, but also from the process of coming-into-being (Figure 6).

Whether handmade or machine-produced, objects can possess the power to move, entrance and evoke fear in us. Yet the particular appeal of handmade objects lies in the human dimension embedded within them: the skill, time and care taken; the tactile, as well as the kinetic association. The garments presented here are of familiar shapes, but put together in an unfamiliar way. They appear ordinary at first glance, yet a closer inspection reveals something unusual in their detail: the woven surface may look pixelated, evoking a comparison between the ubiquitous virtual images on digital interfaces and the tangible surface of textiles, which accentuates the “thingliness” of the surface of a garment; the use of the relatively uncomplicated technique means that the viewers may imagine themselves carrying out the process and consequently appreciate the maker’s time and effort, which appear quantifiable – countable

stitch by stitch. Such particularities are only available to those who pay close attention, maintained beyond the first glance. The garment can thus be considered as a device that reveals the link between the mode of making and of using, the non-objectifiable value of things and relationships, and therefore what counts as “essential luxury” today (Figure 7).

The new luxury

Just as the modernist value of originality was stimulated by a world of increased mechanical reproduction, appreciation of the handmade and the made-to-measure has increased with the over-abundance of disposable goods in the contemporary fashion system. It is as if we are clinging to things that are unique and enduring, which might rescue us from being carried away in the maelstrom of mindless consumption.

As pointed out earlier, these elements often represent the uniqueness of high fashion that distinguishes it from modified, mass-produced versions. However, they exist only as abstract images in some global luxury brands, behind which low-cost labor is exploited for the pursuit of disproportionate added value. Yet also present are numerous other examples which appear to be evidence of “reflexive practice” (both in production and consumption), in which the relationship between making and thinking, craft and industry, designer and technician, maker and user are being critically reassessed.

Emerging in moments of “crisis” are attempts to reappraise and renew existing values. This article does not suggest that the current fashion system should revert to pre-industrial modes of production, nor does it intend to propagate the virtue of the handmade. Today’s appreciation of slowness and first-hand contact is not offered as a solution, but a response symptomatic of the present situation. Just as the “invisible” seam suddenly “appeared” with the attempts to remove it, we may now be more mindfully reflecting on what we produce and consume.

Certain modes of making and using material objects can be our own “rites of passage,” a process of renewal through the marking of the edge, especially within the coexistence of virtual and older types of interaction between person and object, as well as between individuals. This coexistence of abstract and

concrete relationships seems to stimulate the awareness of the link between self and other in contemporary society, and leads us to value a more discrete, coded, self-generated uniqueness. This new value – originating from our fundamental desire to be connected with yet separate from others – may also turn out to be another necessary illusion during a transitional passage, but it is nevertheless a useful indication of the current situation and our creative reaction to it.

NOTES

1. “The reflexivity of modernity, which is directly involved with the continual generating of systematic self-knowledge, does not stabilize the relation between expert knowledge and knowledge applied in lay actions. Knowledge claimed by expert observers rejoins its subject matter, thus altering it” (Giddens 1990: 45).
2. The word ‘contemplate’ derives from Latin *templum*, a space “cut off” or demarcated in which the augur collected and interpreted omens, hence a space consecrated to the gods. Latin word *contemplāre* means to view intensely or long: because, from a temple edifice, the augur can see all around him, whence “to contemplate” (Partridge 2006: 3397–8). The link between the notion of the “sacred” and liminality in an anthropological context is noted by Mary Douglas (2008).
3. “In using the word *culture* I am thinking of the inherited tradition. ... in the common pool of humanity, into which individuals and groups of people may contribute ... in any cultural field it is not possible to be original except on a basis of tradition. ... The interplay between originality and the acceptance of tradition as the basis for inventiveness seems to me to be just one more example... of the interplay between separateness and union” (Winnicott 2005: 133–4).
4. In *Mythologies*, Barthes (1993: 88–90, 88) writes that the way the sections of Bertoni’s Citroën D.S. (F. *Déesse*: goddess) were dovetailed was so impressive that the car appeared to have “obviously fallen from the sky” rather than made by human labor. “... it excites interest less by its substance than by the junction of its components. It is well known that smoothness is always an attribute of perfection because its opposite reveals a technical and typically human

operation of assembling: Christ's robe was seamless, just as the airships of science-fiction are made of unbroken metal".

5. I am referring to the psychoanalytic interpretation of subject/ object formation, based on the tactile interaction with people and material objects within the infant's mothering environment: such as the notion of The Skin Ego postulated by Anzieu, and Winnicott's Transitional Phenomena.

6. Another well-known surrealist image that counteracts automatism is the praying mantis theorized by Caillois (1990, 2003). The striking automatic reflexes in the praying mantis, enabling it to perform vital functions even when decapitated, hauntingly illustrate the infinite automatic imitation without self-reflection resulting in a total loss of the original subject – a behavioral pattern Caillois aptly compares to an automaton.

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Luxury

Figure 1. “Seamless” flared wrap skirt, detail. Photo: Author.

Figure 2. Seaming process. Photo: Author.

Figure 3 “Seamless” dress one, front, detail. Photo: Author.

Figure 4 “Seamless” dress two, in process, detail. Photo: Author.

Figure 5 “Seamless” flared wrap skirt, hem. Photo: Author.

Figure 6 “Seamless” dress one. Photo: Author.

Figure 7 “Seamless” dress two, detail. Photo: Author.